

EXPEDITION REPORT

Expedition dates:
7 July – 16 August 2025

Report published: June 2026

**Mountain ghosts: protecting snow
leopards and other animals of the
Tien Shan mountains of Kyrgyzstan**

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Authors:

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**Matthias Hammer (editor)
Biosphere Expeditions**

Abstract

This study is part of an ongoing annual citizen science expedition to investigate snow leopard *Panthera uncia* and various physical, biological and social aspects that affect the species' conservation. This Biosphere Expeditions snow leopard project has been active for 20 years, making it one of the longest-running initiatives organised by Biosphere Expeditions and one of the most extended research projects on snow leopards ever conducted. Initially, expeditions were based in the Altai mountain range in Russia from 2003 to 2011, contributing to the establishment of Saylyugemsky National Park. From 2014 to 2023, expeditions moved to the Kyrgyz Ala-Too area (Karakol valley) of the Tien Shan mountains, adopting grid-cell surveys and analysis, as well as camera trapping, to reduce data autocorrelation and draw firm distributional conclusions. Due to a lack of local momentum for creating protected areas there, the expedition relocated in 2024 to the Teskey Ala-Too range (Burkhan and Archaly valleys), south of Issyk-Kul Lake and near Sarychat-Eertash Nature Reserve.

The current expedition was conducted from 7 July to 16 August 2025. The total area sampled was roughly 500 square kilometres, divided into 98 sampling units (cells), 2x2 kilometres in size, with elevations ranging from 2,797 to 4,419 metres. Sampling lasted 40 days and engaged a total of 30 citizen scientists over three consecutive 13-day group rotations. The area covered comprised varied topography, from valleys to high mountain ridges and peaks. Herder interviews, community engagement, and local education initiatives were also an integral part of the fieldwork. Most of the tracking cells (93%) were sampled just once.

Snow leopards were recorded in eight cells through camera trapping, DNA scatology, and track identification. Out of nine collected scats presumed to be of snow leopard, DNA analysis confirmed five as snow leopard, identifying three distinct individuals (two males, one female). Overwinter camera trap stations were exceptionally successful, yielding 112 photos across eight cells and confirming at least five unique, identifiable individuals. These multi-season records reflect a network of stable, overlapping resident territories rather than transient movements.

The grey marmot *Marmota baibacina* remained the most ubiquitous prey species, recorded in 79 cells, while Siberian ibex *Capra sibirica* herds were documented across 24 cells, showing a stable resident presence with herd sizes up to 29 individuals. Moles (family *Talpidae*) and Tolai hare *Lepus tolai* also maintained high occupancy. Conversely, the transboundary argali *Ovis ammon* continues to be critically rare, documented in only two cells from a horn and a single camera trap photo. Among carnivores, badger *Meles meles*, red foxe *Vulpes vulpes*, stoat *Mustela erminea* and Mongolian wolf *Canis lupus chanco* were widely recorded. Notably, the elusive Pallas's cat *Otobius manul* was newly confirmed in two distinct cells. Direct evidence of poaching targeting wild ungulates was caught on camera in two cells.

Interviews were conducted with 18 family-based shepherd camps. While herders at higher elevations expressed interest and pride in snow leopard conservation, undercurrents of pasture suspicion and illegal hunting persist. Local communities worked closely with the expedition to supply food and guiding services, benefiting from the alternative tourism income. Shepherds universally cited the wolf as their primary livestock threat, which faces active human persecution. Interviews and field data identified game ungulate poaching, severe overgrazing by thousands-strong sheep herds, and the spread of the invasive shrub *Caragana frutex* as the most severe threats to the ecosystem.

In summary, the wildlife richness found at this study site mirrors broader Central Asian trends, but confirms the Teskey Ala-Too range as a significant, high-density habitat capable of serving as a permanent snow leopard stronghold. To achieve this, regional and national authorities with a permanent presence in Kyrgyzstan must build upon the scientific baselines provided by the expeditions in order to enforce stringent anti-poaching measures and implement community-managed grazing plans.

Корутунду

Бул изилдөө илбирстерди *Panthera uncia* жана бул түрдүн сакталышына таасир эткен ар кандай физикалык, биологиялык жана социалдык аспектилерди изилдөө үчүн жыл сайын өткөрүлүүчү жарандык илимий экспедициянын бир бөлүгү болуп саналат. Бул илбирстерди изилдеген “Биосфералык экспедициялардын” долбоору 20 жылдан бери өз ишин улантууда жана “Биосфералык экспедициялар” тарабынан уюштурулган узак мөөнөттүү долбоор жана жалпысынан илбирстерди изилдеп жаткан эң узакка созулган демилгелердин бири болуп саналат. Алгач экспедициялар 2003-2011-жылдары Россиянын Алтай тоолорунда жүргүзүлүп, Сайлюгем улуттук паркынын түзүлүшүнө салымын кошкон. 2014-2023-жылдары экспедициялар Тянь-Шань тоолорундагы Кыргыз Ала-Тоо кыркасынын аймагына (Каракөл өрөөнү) көчүп барган. Ал жерде корголгон аймактарды түзүү үчүн жергиликтүү түрткүнүн жоктугунан улам, экспедиция 2024-жылы Ысык-Көлдүн түштүгүндөгү жана Сарычат-Ээрташ жаратылыш коругунун жанындагы Тескей Ала-тоо кыркасына (Бурхан жана Арчали өрөөндөрү) көчүрүлгөн.

Каралып жаткан экспедиция 2025-жылдын 7-июлунан 16-августуна чейин жүргүзүлгөн. Изилденген аймактын жалпы аянты болжол менен 500 чарчы километрди түзүп, узуну, туурасы 2x2 километрди түзгөн 98 үлгү алуучу клеткаларга бөлүнгөн. Аймактын бийиктик амплитудасы 2797 метрден 4419 метрге чейин жетет. Изилдөө 40 күнгө созулду жана жалпысынан 30 жарандык окумуштуу кезеги менен үч жолу 13 күндүк топтук ротацияларды жүргүзүштү. Аймактын рельефи ар түрдүү – өрөөндөрдөн кырка тоо жана чокуларга чейин өзгөрөт. Малчылар менен маектешүү, жергиликтүү коомчулуктун катышуусу жана билим берүү демилгелери да талаа жумуштарынын ажырагыс бөлүгү болгон. Изилденген клеткалардын көпчүлүгү (93%) болгону бир жолу каралган.

Илбирстер сегиз клеткада фототузактары, кыктарынын ДНКсы жана изин аныктоо аркылуу катталган. Илибирсти деп божомолдонуп чогултулган кыктардын тогуз үлгүсүнүн ичинен ДНК анализинин жыйынтыгы боюнча, бешөө илибирсти деп аныкталган. Терең изилдөөлөрдүн жыйынтыгы боюнча үч үлгүнүн ичинен экөө эркек, бирөө ургаачыныкы экендиги тастыкталды. Кышкага калтырылган фототузактардан алынган сүрөттөр өзгөчө ийгиликтүү болду. Сегиз фототузактан илбирстердин 112 сүрөттөрү тартылып, кеминде беш илбирс тастыкталды. Бул көп жылдык байкоолор убактылуу кыймылдар гана эмес, туруктуу, бири-бирине кесилишкен илбирстердин ареалынын тармактарынын бар экенин чагылдырат.

Суур 79 клеткада катталып, аймакта эң көп санда таралган олжо түрү бойдон калууда. Ал эми эчки-текелердин үйүрлөрү 29 башка чейин жетип, 24 клеткада катталган. Бул көрсөткүчтөр аталган түрлөрдүн санынын туруктуу экендигин тастыктайт. Сокур чычкандар (29 клетка) жана коёндор (28 клетка) да көп санда катталган. Бул түрлөрдөн айырмаланып, тескерисинче аркар-кулжалар өтө сейрек кездешүүчү түрү бойдон калууда. Алар мүйүздөрү жана фототузак аркылуу болгону эки клеткада катталган. Жырткыч жаныбарлардын ичинен кашкулак (20 клетка), түлкү (15 клетка) жана суусар (14 клеткада) кеңири таралган. Белгилей кетчү нерсе, мадыл эки клеткада фотопкапкандын жардамы менен аныкталды. Жапайы туяктуу жаныбарларга карата аңчылык кылуунун түздөн-түз далили эки клеткада фототузактардын жардамы менен түшүрүлгөн.

Экспедиция учурунда үй-бүлөөсү менен жашаган 18 малчы менен сурамжылоолор жүргүзүлгөн. Бийик тоолордогу малчылар жаратылышты коргоого кызыгуусун жана аны менен сыймыктануусун билдиришүүдө, Ошол эле учурда жайыттарга терс таасир жана мыйзамсыз аңчылык кылуу уланууда. Жергиликтүү коомчулук экспедиция менен тыгыз кызматташып, азык-түлүк жана гиддик кызматтарды камсыз кылышкан. Малчылар карышкырды малга негизги коркунуч катары карашып, адам баласы тарабынан куугунтукталган негизги түр деп белгилешкен. Сурамжылоолор жана талаа маалыматтары боюнча, мыйзамсыз аңчылык, жайыттын ыксыз пайдаланылуусу жана инвазивдүү төө куйруктардын жайылышы экосистемага эң чоң коркунуч туудурууда.

Кыскача айтканда, бул изилдөө аймагында табылган жапайы жаратылыштын байлыгы Борбордук Азияда болуп жаткан кеңири тенденцияны чагылдырат. Тескей Ала-Тоосунда илбирстердин салыштырмалуу жыш популяциясы байкалгандыктан бул аймак илбирстердин туруктуу таянычы экендиги тастыкталат. Бул максатка жетүү үчүн Кыргызстанда жергиликтүү жана улуттук бийлик өкүлдөрү мыйзамсыз аңчылыкка каршы катуу чараларды көрүү жана коомчулук тарабынан башкарылган жайытты колдонууну пландоону ишке ашыруу үчүн экспедициялардын илимий негиздерине таянуусу керек.

Резюме

Данное исследование является частью ежегодной гражданской научной экспедиции по изучению снежного барса *Panthera uncia* и различных физических, биологических и социальных аспектов, влияющих на сохранение данного вида. Настоящий проект “Биосферные экспедиции”, посвященный изучению снежных барсов, существует уже 20 лет, что делает его одной из самых продолжительных инициатив, когда-либо организованных “Биосферными экспедициями”, и одним из самых продолжительных исследовательских проектов по снежным барсам. Впервые экспедиции были проведены в 2003-2011 годах в Алтайских горах в России и способствовали созданию Сайлюгемского национального парка. В 2014-2023 годах экспедиции переместились в Кыргызский Ала-Тоо (Каракольская долина) в горах Тянь-Шаня. Из-за отсутствия местных стимулов для создания там охраняемых территорий экспедиция в 2024 году переместилась на хребет Тескей Ала-Тоо (долины Бурхан и Арчалы), к югу от озера Иссык-Куль и недалеко от природного заповедника Сарычат-Ээрташ.

Рассматриваемая экспедиция проводилась с 7 июля по 16 августа 2025 года. Общая площадь, ареала исследования составила примерно 500 квадратных километров и была разделена на 98 единиц ячеек размером 2x2 километра с амплитудами высот от 2797 до 4419 метров. Исследование длилось 40 дней, и в трех последовательных 13-дневных сменах групп приняли участие в общей сложности 30 гражданских ученых. Ареал исследования имел разнообразный рельеф – от долин до высоких горных хребтов и вершин. Опросы скотоводов, вовлечение местного сообщества и образовательные инициативы также были неотъемлемой частью полевых работ. Большинство (93%) ячеек были изучены всего один раз.

Снежные барсы были замечены в восьми клетках с помощью фотоловушек, анализа ДНК экскрементов и идентификации следов. Из девяти собранных экскрементов, предположительно принадлежащих снежному барсу, анализ ДНК подтвердил принадлежность пяти особей к снежному барсу, идентифицировав трех отдельных особей (двух самцов и одну самку). Снимки от фотоловушек, оставленные на зиму оказались исключительно удачными: в восьми камерах было сделано 112 снимков, на которых были зафиксированы по меньшей мере пять уникальных, поддающихся идентификации особей. Эти многолетние фиксации отражают о наличии сетей стабильных, не временные перемещения, а пересекающихся ареалов обитания.

Серый сурок остаётся самым распространенным видом добычи, зарегистрированным в 79 клетках, в то время как стада сибирских козогов (до 29 особей) были зафиксированы в 24 клетках, что свидетельствует о стабильном постоянном присутствии в данном ареале. Кроты (29 ячеек) и толай-зайцы (28 ячеек) также сохранили высокую популяцию. И наоборот, в отличие этих видов архары по-прежнему остаются крайне редким видом, зафиксированным только в двух ячейках с рогом и на одной фотографии с фотоловушки. Среди хищных животных были широко зарегистрированы барсуки (20 клеток), лисы (15 клеток), каменные куницы (14 клеток) и волки (14 клеток). Примечательно, что недавно было подтверждено присутствие неуловимого манула в двух разных клетках. Прямые доказательства браконьерства, нацеленного на диких копытных, были зафиксированы на камеру в двух фотоловушках.

Были проведены интервью с 18 скотоводами с семейными пастушьими стойбищами. В то время как пастухи, живущие на больших высотах, выразили заинтересованность и гордость в сохранении снежного барса, в то же время сохраняются пагубное влияние на пастбища и незаконные охоты. Местные общины тесно сотрудничали с экспедицией в поставках продовольствия и услуг гида, извлекая выгоду из альтернативного дохода от туризма. Пастухи повсеместно называли волка главной угрозой для своего скота, который подвергается активному преследованию со стороны людей. Опросы и полевые данные выявили браконьерство в отношении копытных животных, чрезмерный выпас скота многотысячными стадами овец и распространение инвазивного караганника в качестве наиболее серьезных угроз экосистеме.

Таким образом, богатство дикой природы, обнаруженное на этом исследовательском участке, отражает более широкие тенденции в Центральной Азии, но подтверждает, что хребет Терскей Ала-Тоо является значительным местом обитания с высокой плотностью популяции, способным служить постоянным оплотом снежного барса. Для достижения этой цели региональные и национальные органы власти Кыргызстана должны опираться на научные данные, полученные в ходе экспедиций, чтобы обеспечить соблюдение строгих мер по борьбе с браконьерством и реализовать планы выпаса скота, управляемые общинами.

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1. Expedition Review

M. Hammer (editor)
Biosphere Expeditions

1.1. Background

This study was part of an ongoing annual citizen science expedition to study snow leopards *Panthera uncia* and physical, biological and social aspects that affect the species. Expeditions in Central Asia were first based in the Altai mountain range in Russia from 2003 to 2011. From 2014 onwards, expeditions moved to the Tien Shan mountains in Kyrgyzstan, first to Karakol valley in the Kyrgyz Ala-Too range (2014-2023), and since 2024 the Jyluu-Suu, Burkhan and Archaly valleys near the Teskey Ala-Too range (Figure 1.1a).

All technical/scientific expedition reports and peer-reviewed papers about the Altai years can be found [here](#), and about the Tien Shan years [here](#).

Figure 1.1a. Schematic map of current and previous snow leopard expedition sites in Central Asia.

1.2. Research area

The research area is as described in [Zholdoshbekov and Hammer \(2024\)](#) and chapter 2.1. below.

1.3. Dates & team

The expedition ran over a period of six weeks divided into three 13-day group rotations, each composed of a team of national and international citizen scientists, a professional scientist and an expedition leader. Group dates were as shown in the team list below.

The expedition team was recruited by Biosphere Expeditions and consisted of a mixture of ages, nationalities and backgrounds. They were (in alphabetical order and with country of residence):

7 – 19 July 2025

Aurélie de Brujin (Netherlands), Sarah Coad (USA), Vanessa Homewood (USA), Rupa Kapitzki (UAE), Ivo Alexander Kapitzki (UAE), Annalena Klein (Germany), Johan Mees (Netherlands), Thomas Panzl (Austria), Andrea Schmid (Germany), Heike Vornhagen (Ireland).

21 July – 2 August 2025

Abdulaziz Alkaboob (Saudi Arabia), Kirstin Blös (Germany), Gianni Buschini (Switzerland), Kath Danaher (New Zealand), Constantin Dunker (Germany), Anne Heemann (Germany), Mary Kitchen (UK), Eva Klages (Germany), David Mullan (USA), Marjam Salehzadeh (Germany).

4 – 16 August 2025

Micha Akchoti (Germany), Kathleen Byrnes (Australia), Patricia Gordon (Australia), Jacob Gresh (USA), Ana Hernández (USA), Emma Kruijswijk (Netherlands), Chai Hong Lim (UK), Wera Müllers (Germany), Celina Rudolf (Canada), Klaus Würth (Germany).

The expedition scientist and co-author of this report was Emilbek Zholdoshbekov, the expedition leaders were Johnny Adams and Matthias Hammer (group 1) and Darran Keogh (groups 2 & 3). Also involved were local people Taalai Mukanbetov (guide), Aizat Abdrakhmanova (cook) and Zhoomart Taalaibekov (logistics & transport).

A medical umbrella, safety and evacuation procedures were in place, but did not have to be invoked as there were no medical, health or safety incidences that required outside help.

1.4. Acknowledgements

We are grateful to the expedition participants, who not only dedicated their spare time to helping but also, through their expedition contributions, funded the research. Thank you also to Maksat Mukanbetov and his brother Taalai Mukanbetov from the study site community for their advice and guidance. Thank you also to Almaz Alzhambaev of www.carforrent.kg, the Friends of Biosphere Expeditions and all donors to a fundraising campaign for their support.

1.5. Further information & enquiries

More background information on Biosphere Expeditions in general and on this expedition in particular including pictures, diary excerpts and more can be found on the Biosphere Expeditions website www.biosphere-expeditions.org. Enquiries should be addressed to Biosphere Expeditions at the address given on the website.

A copy of this and all other reports and scientific publications produced by or in association with this expedition can be found on the [Biosphere Expeditions ResearchGate page](#). A copy of the diary of this expedition is on the [Biosphere Expeditions blog page](#).

1.6. Expedition budget

Each citizen scientist participant paid towards expedition costs a contribution of € 2,990 per person per 13-day group. The contribution covered accommodation and meals, supervision and induction, special research equipment and all transport from and to the team assembly point. It did not cover excess luggage charges, travel insurance, personal expenses such as telephone bills, souvenirs etc., or visa and other travel expenses to and from the assembly point (e.g. international flights). Details on how this contribution was spent are given below.

Income	€
Expedition contributions	97,087
Expenditure	
Expedition base includes all food & services	15,889
Transport includes hire cars, fuel, taxis and buses in Kyrgyzstan	13,907
Equipment and hardware includes research materials & gear etc. purchased internationally & locally	2,856
Staff includes local and Biosphere Expeditions staff salaries and travel expenses	16,112
Administration & research includes miscellaneous fees & sundries, DNA analysis & other research costs	4,783
Team recruitment Tien Shan as estimated % of annual PR costs for Biosphere Expeditions	11,223
Income – Expenditure	32,317
Total percentage spent directly on project	67%

2. Monitoring snow leopards and other species on the south side of the Teskey Ala-Too mountain range in the Tien Shan mountains of Kyrgyzstan

2.1. Background, materials and methods

The background to the expedition, its materials and methods and training of citizen scientists, data collection and analysis are all described in [Zholdoshbekov and Hammer \(2025\)](#). A 2x2 km grid was used to document presence or absence of species.

Figure 2.1a. shows base camp and the terrain of the study site, including names of principal rivers and mountain ranges. Figure 2.1b shows the 98 2 x 2 km cells surveyed, with rivers, expedition base camp, camera trap locations and unpaved roads. Colours indicate which expedition group surveyed which cells.

Nineteen digital camera traps (Bushnell 8MP and Bushnell 14MP, Figure 2.2c, Appendix I) were installed in locations that Jackson et al. (2006) identified as those with the best chance to capture snow leopards, sixteen of these had been in place since a reconnaissance expedition in 2023 left them there. Spatial data were analysed in ESRI ArcGIS 10.8 software. A pansharpened Landsat 8 imagery with spatial resolution 15 m (acquired on 22 July 2025) georeferenced topography map was used to overlay data. The map was then given a terrain shadow effect, created by ALOS PALSAR DEM with spatial resolution 12.5 m, to highlight differences in topography. Resulting camera trap images were analysed and categorised manually by human researchers. All snow leopard images were also uploaded to [whiskerbook.org](#), which provides an AI-driven matching algorithm, comparing all images uploaded to each other, as well as to images uploaded by other researchers.

Snow leopard signs such as tracks, scrapes and scent-sprayed locations were also searched for. Presumed snow leopard scats were collected for DNA analysis to species (not individual) level, which was performed by the [Senckenberg Institute's Centre for Wildlife Genetics](#) in Germany. Most other species of interest had their scats identified by sight without confirmation by DNA analysis, which is expensive.

Species of interest included: (1) Species that, when present, are highly detectable by the methods employed, meaning that a substantial dataset can be obtained to infer basic population dynamics. Examples include the two key prey species ibex and marmot. (2) Species that are likely to be detected when present, but are often not, indicating habitat modification and human interference. Examples include one important prey species, the argali, and also the wolf, lynx, brown bear and deer species. Other species were also circumstantially recorded, such as weasel, vole and badger.

Shepherd interviews were conducted using a [standardised interview datasheet](#) within an informal, casual conversation. Location of camera traps and other research methods were not shared with local shepherds. Instead – and while conducting interviews – an emphasis was placed on fostering friendly relations in what the expedition scientist termed “Kymyz (local specialty of fermented horse milk) diplomacy”. Conversations with children about the importance of nature conservation were another focus.

Figure 2.1a. Study area. Terrain shadow and isolines were generated using ALOS PALSAR DEM, glaciers using RGI shapefiles (WGS 84 datum).

Figure 2.1b. Map of the study area showing the 98 2 x 2 km cells surveyed, with rivers, expedition base camp, camera trap locations and unpaved roads. Terrain shadow generated by using ALOS PALSAR DEM and for glacier polygons used RGI glacier inventory. Colours indicate which expedition group surveyed which cells.

2.2. Results

Overall results

The expedition lasted 40 days (7 July – 16 August 2025) and sampled 392 square kilometres, divided into 98 sampling units (cells) 2x2 kilometres in size, with elevations ranging from 2,797 to 4,419 meters. Sampling was conducted by citizen scientists, staff and local people as mentioned in chapter 1.3. Capacity-building and education initiatives were also part of the expedition. Most of the cells (93%) were sampled just once.

Snow leopards were recorded in eight cells, by means of camera trapping, DNA scatology and track identification. Of the nine scats collected and presumed to be of snow leopards, DNA analysis revealed that five originated from snow leopard and one each from fox and wolf. For two samples, the species could not be determined due to contamination.

Marmot was the most frequently recorded prey species (79 cells), followed by ibex (24), mole (29) and hare (28). Argali, on the other hand, was recorded in only two cells, from camera trap and horn. Badger (20) and wolf (13) were the most recorded carnivores. Direct evidence of poaching activities of ibex and argali was found by camera traps. Camera trap pictures were delivered to the ranger responsible for the area for identification of poachers.

Seventeen shepherd camps (out of a total of 93) were visited for interviews. Most shepherds were found to be suspicious of wildlife conservation efforts, most likely because they have concerns that this would reveal their own poaching activities, which include retaliatory killings and efforts to create favourable conditions for their large (over)grazing herds.

Snow leopard *Panthera uncia*

Camera traps were extraordinarily successful in capturing snow leopards in eight cells, taking 112 pictures of five different, identifiable individuals (see below), representing 3.26% of all photographed wild animals. Photos were taken in August, September, October and November 2024 and in March, April, May, June and July 2025.

Five scats confirmed to be of snow leopard by DNA analysis were found in two high-altitude cells on high ridges or peaks. Two scats were not good enough to be analysed down to individual level, but three scats were found to be from three individuals, two males PMSat001m and PMSat003m, and one female PMSat002f.

Suspected snow leopard tracks were found in two cells O-10 and O-13. However, tracks are notoriously difficult to identify reliably with high error rates (Johansson et al. 2020).

Table 2.2a and Figure 2.1a summarise snow leopard detections by cell and method, giving further details of each detection.

Table 2.2a. Snow leopard detections by the expedition (CT = camera trap, SL = snow leopard).

Cell	Detection by camera trap	Detection by DNA scatology	Altitude (m)	Habitat	Remarks
K-07	CT BE08 & BE13 23 photos 3 individuals (probably), one individual B and one C	3 scats confirmed SL, 2 good enough for detection of individuals PMSat001m (male) PMSat002f (female)	3930 & 3872	Mountain ridge	Trap in place Aug 2024 – Jul 2025, photos captured on 15.10.2024 morning, 28.05.2025 afternoon, 27.06.2025 afternoon, 13.07.2025 morning
	L-12	CT BE16 6 photos 2 individuals (one indiv. B) CT BE18 6 photos 2 individuals (one indiv. B, one D?)	2 scats confirmed SL, 1 good enough for detection of individual PMSat003m (male) Scat and camera traps 1.3 km apart along a ridge		3976
L-13	CT BE02 3 photos 1 individual (A)	None	3959	Saddle ridge	Trap in place Aug 2024 – Jul 2025, photos captured on 13.07.2025 evening
O-09	CT BE15 65 photos 4 individuals (probably), one of them individual D	None	3935	Mountain ridge	Trap in place Aug 2024 – Jul 2025, photos captured on 23.09.2024 noon 08.03.2025 afternoon 19.03.2025 afternoon 27.04.2025 night 07.05.2025 morning 20.06.2025 night
O-11	CT BE24 3 photos 2 individuals (probably)	None	3937	Mountain ridge	Trap in place Aug 2024 – Jul 2025, photo capture on 28.03.2025 morning 30.04.2025 afternoon
O-13	CT BE25 3 photos 1 individual	None	3777	Mountain ridge	Trap in place Aug 2023* – Jul 2025, photo capture on 24.09.2024 afternoon
P-10	CT BE35 3 photos 2 individuals (probably), one individual E	None	3900	Saddle ridge	Trap in place Aug 2024 – Jul 2025, photo capture on 04.11.2024 afternoon

*Camera trap left in place by 2023 expedition

Legend

- Rivers
- Surveyed cells
- Snow leopard
- CT, SC Animal record type

Figure 2.2a. Snow leopard detection in cells. CT = camera trap, SC = scat, TR = track.

Individual identification of snow leopards through camera trap pictures is possible by the size and location of spots on the fur, especially on the paws, sides, the upper surface of the tail, as well as the forehead (Blowqvist et al. 1980). In addition, whiskerbook.org provides an AI-driven matching algorithm, comparing all images uploaded to each other, as well as to images uploaded by other researchers. All camera trap images were processed and analysed using these methods, with a human checking all results as final arbiter, yielding identification of individuals in some cases as follows:

The snow leopard captured by camera trap BE02 (13 July 2025, cell L-13) has unique patterns on its tail, hind legs and spine, so it was identified as **individual A**.

Figure 2.2b. Individual A as captured by camera trap BE02.

The snow leopard captured by camera trap BE13 (on 15 October 2024, 28 May 2025 and 27 June 2025, all in cell K-07), was identified as the same **individual B** by its identical coat pattern as shown in Figure 2.2c. The match was done by a human; Whiskerbook failed to make this match.

Figure 2.2c. Individual B as captured by camera trap BE13.

It is likely that **individual B** was also captured by camera traps BE16 (Figure 2.2d) and BE18 (Figure 2.2e), both in cell L-12, which stood roughly 400 metres apart. Captures took place on 16 August 2024 and 9 September 2024, each time roughly 20 minutes apart. This makes it highly likely that the same individual B was captured each time. Capture angles and therefore movement patterns were also a close match on each camera trap. The match with the BE13 captures is based on similarities in coat pattern, as well as temporal and spatial association (BE13 and BE16/18 are approximately 10 km apart). These matches were made by a human; Whiskerbook failed to make matches.

Figure 2.2d. Individual B as captured by camera trap BE16.

DNA scatology identified three individuals - two males and one female - in cells K-07 and L-12 at the camera trap sites (see Table 2.2a), about 10 km apart.

Figure 2.2e. Individual B as captured by camera trap BE18.

BE15 also captured a snow leopard on 08 March 2025 and 7 May 2025 in cell O-09. Similar coat patterns at the base of the tail suggest this is unique **individual C**, clearly different from A and B.

Figure 2.2f. Individual C as captured by camera trap BE15.

Camera trap BE15 in cell O-09 on 19 March 2025 captured a snow leopard with an unusual pattern on its tail (see Figure 2.2g) that differed from all the other individuals. The unique facial coat pattern matched with the snow leopard captured by the same camera trap on 27 April 2025. This is therefore **individual D**, matched by a human.

Figure 2.2g. Individual D as captured by camera trap BE15.

The same camera trap BE15 also captured one individual (as marked by similar coat pattern on the right flank) twice within three hours on 20 June 2025. This coat pattern could not be matched to any other individual, but we are listing it here under a **speculative re-capture of individual D** by BE15 within a time period of three months.

Figure 2.2h. Speculative re-capture of individual D by camera trap BE15.

The snow leopard captured by camera trap BE18 on 6 June 2025 in cell L-12 (about 10 km from camera trap BE15 in cell O-09) has tail similarities with D and is therefore considered another **speculative re-capture of individual D**.

The snow leopard captured in a remarkable series of images by camera trap BE35 on 4 November 2024 in cell P-09 has no similarities with other animals and is therefore considered **individual E** (Figure 2.2i).

Figure 2.2i. Individual E as captured by camera trap BE35.

Other captures by various camera traps in the study site (see Figure 2.2j & k) could not be assigned, because they were too blurry or showed only small parts of the animal.

Figure 2.2j (first row) & k (second row). Snow leopard captures by various camera traps that could not be assigned.

Ibex Capra sibirica

Ibex was recorded in a total of 24 cells (Table 2.2b, Figure 2.2I), often by multiple means. Camera trap images (Figures 2.2m-p) were taken in 12 cells during the day, indicating a diurnal lifestyle. Scat was detected in 13 cells, tracks were found in 11 cells, and horns and skulls in four cells.

Table 2.2b. Ibex detection records during the expedition.

Cell number	Detection method	Detection result
H-10	Sign	Scat, track
I-02	Sign	Scat, horn
I-04	Sign	Scat, track
I-05	Sign	Scat, track
I-13	Sign	Scat, track
J-02	Sign	Track
J-05	Camera trap BE-14	3 individuals
J-06	Sign, Camera trap BE-06	Scat, 14 individuals
K-05	Sign	Skull
K-07	Camera trap BE-13	2 herds (~15-20 individuals for each)
L-12	Camera trap BE-18	1 individual (male)
L-13	Camera trap BE-02	2 individuals
L-13	Signs	Scat, track
L-14	Signs	Scat, track
O-09	Camera trap BE-15	29 individuals
O-11	Camera trap BE-24	17 individuals
O-13	Signs, Camera trap BE-25*	Scat, track, 7 individuals
O-14	Sign	Skull
P-08	Camera trap BE-14	3 individuals
P-09	Signs, Camera trap BE-35	Scat, track, 8 individuals
Q-08	Signs, Camera trap BE-07	Scat, track, 14 individuals
R-08	Camera trap BE-34	5 individuals
T-06	Sign	Scat
T-07	Sign	Skull
W-05	Sign	Track

*Camera trap left in place by 2023 expedition

Legend

— Rivers Surveyed cells Ibex CT, SC Animal record type

Figure 2.21. Ibex detection in cells. CT = camera trap, HO = horns, SC = scat, SK = skull, TR = track.

Figure 2.2m. Ibex recorded by camera traps BE-02 / BE-06 / BE-08.

Figure 2.2n. Ibex recorded by camera traps BE-13 / BE-14 / BE-15.

Figure 2.2o. Ibex recorded by camera traps BE-18 / BE-24.

Figure 2.2p. Ibex recorded by camera traps BE-25 / BE-30.

Argali Ovis ammon

Argali was recorded in two cells, from horns, and in another from a single camera trap picture (see Figures 2.2q & r). There were no direct sightings of argali.

Legend

- Rivers
- Surveyed cells
- Argali
- CT, SC Animal record type

Figure 2.2q. Argali detection in cells. CT = camera trap, HO = horns.

Figure 2.2r. Argali recorded by camera trap BE-15.

Marmot *Marmota baibacina*

Marmot was recorded in 80 cells (Figure 2.2t) by direct sighting (42 cells), camera trap (1 cell, Figure 2.2s), scat (58 cells), call (6 cells), burrows (36 cells) and track (10 cells).

Legend

- Rivers
- Surveyed cells
- Marmot
- CT, SC Animal record type

Figure 2.2s. Marmot detection in cells.
 CT = camera trap, DS = direct sighting, SC = scat, BU = burrow, CL = call, TR = track.

33F1C

04-26-2025 10:21:50

Figure 2.2t. Marmot recorded by camera trap BE-15.

Tolai Hare *Lepus tolai*

Tolai hare was recorded in 28 cells: in one cell each by direct sighting and scat, in 24 cells by scat only, and by camera traps BE-14 and BE-15 (Figure 2.2v) at night in two cells, and by tracks in one cell.

Legend

— Rivers Surveyed cells Tolai hare CT, SC Animal record type

Figure 2.2u. , Tolai hare detection in cells.
 CT = camera trap, DS = direct sighting, SC = scat, TR = track.

Figure 2.2v. Tolai hare recorded by camera trap BE-14 / BE-15.

Mongolian wolf *Canis lupus chanco*

Mongolian wolf was recorded in 14 cells (Figure 2.2w) from scats, camera trap (Figure 2.2x) and a [direct sighting](#) (Figure 2.2y). Of the nine scat samples thought to be from snow leopard and submitted to DNA analysis, one was from wolf, the other scat samples were identified by shape and smell.

Legend

— Rivers Surveyed cells Wolf CT, SC Animal record type

Figure 2.2w. Mongolian wolf detection in cells. CT = camera trap, DS = direct sighting, SC = scat.

Figure 2.2x. Mongolian wolf recorded by camera traps BE-06 and BE-15.

Figure 2.2y. Mongolian wolf with prey game in its mouth.
 © Marjam Salehzadeh – also see her [video](#) of the encounter.

Red fox *Vulpes vulpes*

Fox was recorded in fifteen cells (Figure 2.2z). Camera trapping recorded seven foxes mostly at night (Figures 2.2aa–ac). Scat samples (unconfirmed by DNA analysis) were found in one cell.

Legend

— Rivers Surveyed cells Fox CT, SC Animal record type

Figure 2.2z. Fox detection in cells. CT = camera trap, SC = scat, TR = track.

Figure 2.2aa. Fox recorded by camera traps BE-06 / BE-07 / BE-08.

Figure 2.2ab. Fox recorded by camera traps BE-13 / BE-15 / BE-16.

Bushnell

08-01-2025 16:30:32

Figure 2.2ac. Fox recorded by camera traps BE-06.

Pallas's cat (manul) *Otocolobus manul*

Pallas's cat (manul) was detected in two cells (Figure 2.2ad) by camera traps BE-15 and BE-16 (Figure 2.2ae).

Legend

— Rivers Surveyed cells Manul CT, SC Animal record type

Figure 2.2ad. Pallas's cat (manul) detection in cells. CT = camera trap

Figure 2.2ae. Pallas's cat (manul) recorded by camera traps BE-15 / BE-16.

Stone marten *Martes foina*

Stone marten was recorded in fourteen cells (Figure 2.2af), in one cell by direct sighting, in six cells by camera traps (Figures 2.2ag-ah), in seven cells by scat and in one cell by burrows. All images were taken at night.

Legend

- Rivers
- Surveyed cells
- Stone marten
- CT, SC Animal record type

Figure 2.2af. Stone marten detection in cells by BU = burrow, DS = direct sight, CT = camera trap, SC = scat.

Figure 2.2ag. Stone marten recorded by camera traps BE-08 / BE-15.

Figure 2.2ah. Stone marten recorded by camera traps BE-16 / BE-19 / BE-35.

Stoat *Mustela erminea*

Stoat was recorded in one cell by direct sighting (Figure 2.2aj) and in one cell by scat and track (Figure 2.2ai).

Legend

- Rivers
- Surveyed cells
- Steppe polecat
- CT, SC Animal record type

Figure 2.2ai. Stoat detection in cells by DS = direct sighting, SC = scat, TR = track.

Figure 2.2aj. Stoat at base camp © Klaus Würth.

Badger *Meles leucurus*

Badger was recorded in 20 cells (Figure 2.2ak), mostly from scats (17 cells), but also by camera trap BE-09 (Figure 2.2al).

Legend

— Rivers Surveyed cells Badger CT, SC Animal record type

Figure 2.2ak. Badger detection in cells by DS = direct sighting, CT = camera trap, SC = scat, BU = burrow, CL = call, TR = track.

Figure 2.2a1. Badger recorded by camera trap BE-09.

Moles *Talpida* sp.

Moles were recorded in 29 cells, mostly from burrows (Figure 2.2am).

Legend

- Rivers
- Surveyed cells
- Mole
- CT, SC Animal record type

Figure 2.2am. Mole detection in cells by BU = burrow, SC = scat and TR = track.

Rodent, mainly Tien Shan birch mouse *Sicista tianshanica*

Rodents were recorded in 36 cells (Figure 2.2an), mainly by burrows, except for direct sightings in 7 cells and scats in 19 cells.

Legend

- Rivers
- Surveyed cells
- Mouse
- CT, SC Animal record type

Figure 2.2an. Rodent detection in cells by BU = burrow, DS = direct sighting and SC = scat, TR = track.

Shepherd interviews & community engagement

Following the method and [standardised interview datasheet](#) described in Zholdosbekov and Hammer (2024), 18 shepherds (different from those interviewed in 2024) were interviewed, 15 in Burkhan valley and two in Archaly valley (Figure 2.2ao).

Figure 2.2ao. Location of 17 shepherd homesteads where interviews were conducted, 15 of them in Burkhan valley, two in Archaly valley.

A summary of interview results is presented in Table 2.2c.

Table 2.2c. Summary of interview results. Findings that are new since 2024 are shown in italics. SL = snow leopard.

Age	25-60, average 41
Gender	11 (61%) male, 7 (39%) female
Occupation	All but one interviewee specified “shepherd”, only one “herder”. The difference is semantic. It is noteworthy that all of them are employed by a livestock owner to herd livestock that is not their own. Their typical day consists of herding and dairy production, which does not appear to be tied to gender. <i>In addition to herding livestock, shepherds are engaged in subsistence farming around their homesteads.</i>
Livestock herded	The mainstay is large flocks of sheep, supplemented mainly by cow and horse and occasionally by goat and donkey. There was only one yak herder who did not have sheep. It is important to note that there is an incentive to understate the size of flocks to save on taxes. This is likely to have been the case here too, corroborated by visual spot checks.
Herding practices	Most herders in Burkhan valley work together with their families in the study site every year between May and October. <i>In Archaly valley, herders interviewed said that they stay on site for the whole year.</i>
SL knowledge/ experience	Four interviewees claimed (credibly) to have seen a SL, none of them could provide proof of this. Four interviewees (22%) claimed that people they know have seen SL. Four interviewees (22%) had heard of SL attacking livestock. None of the interviewees had an idea of how many SL live in Kyrgyzstan.
SL impact	A minority of interviewees (5 / 27%) believe that SL has no impact on them or their livelihoods, or they had no opinion on this. 11 (61%) believe that SL has a beneficial impact and only two (11%) cited a detrimental impact. <i>Strangely, herders living furthest from SL habitat, had the most negative opinion of them.</i> The most interesting answers were that SL in low numbers are beneficial, but detrimental in high numbers. This is corroborated by the answers about how people feel about SL. The majority (16 / 89%) thought that there is no danger to people from SL attacks, the rest did not know or did not give an answer. There was also little concern about game or small animal impact through SL predation, but livestock impact was a concern for seven (39%).
Feelings towards SL	78% (14) believe that SL is good for Kyrgyzstan and there was some clear pride expressed for this emblematic animal. 78% (14) thought that SL should be protected in Kyrgyzstan. However, it is also evident that there is a very clear limit to that pride and support, that ends when the animal attacks livestock.
SL and tourism / the expedition	There is a clear interest in alternative sources of income through SL presence. 67% (12) believe that SL attracting tourism was a good thing. 61% (11) were interested in helping the expedition, mainly by providing food (28% / 5) and also through handicrafts (11% / 2) and services such as horse rental, facilities and guiding (22% / 4). <i>Shepherds who own lorries all declared they were ready to help with logistics.</i> The expedition ended up utilising all of these offer types. A sizeable minority (17% / 3) wanted to find out more about the expedition’s work by attending an information evening at base camp.
Other comments	Since Soviet times, wolves are considered a much bigger problem than SL and are universally loathed and persecuted, with state bounties paid for kills.

Interviews in 2025 concentrated on higher altitude homesteads, where exposure to snow leopard depredation was likely to be greater. Curiously, interest in and tolerance of wildlife, including snow leopard, appeared to be higher in those locations, which is the opposite of what we expected. Instead, occupants of lower altitude homesteads further away from wilderness areas, had less interest in and tolerance of wildlife, including snow leopard.

When women were interviewed, they universally referred to their husbands and sons for information on wildlife and wilderness. For example, Mrs. Nurgul said that her husband “knows a lot about the environment, but he is in the village now, so come back later”. This is because the traditional role of women in the homesteads is to cook and tend the homestead; it is the men who perform herding tasks away from the homestead.

In addition, the expedition engaged the local community in biodiversity conservation and expedition activities wherever possible (guiding, logistics services, buying food and food products, souvenirs for the citizen scientists etc.) to generate value and income. The expedition also attended community gatherings, presenting its mission to those present and talking about the importance of nature conservation for livelihoods based on livestock grazing. The expedition also invited the local community to base camp to talk about the same topics. This happened twice with approximately 150 people attending each time. Finally, the expedition routinely collected rubbish whilst out on fieldwork.

2.3. Discussion

Snow leopard

The findings presented here are a major milestone in understanding snow leopard population dynamics within the region, showing a significant expansion in data density and geographical scope compared to previous years. Historically, the project's efforts in the Kyrgyz Ala-Too range (2014–2023) focused primarily on presence/absence data, yielding limited annual records—such as only one camera trap photo and one DNA-confirmed scat across 76 cells in 2022 (Mambetov & Hammer 2023). Following the 2024 relocation to the Teskey Ala-Too range (Burkhan and Archaly valleys), documentation improved with 18 photographic captures across four camera traps (Zholdoshbekov & Hammer 2025). This 2025 dataset, however, establishes a true regional baseline by recording 17 detections across 113 camera trap pictures captured by 9 different camera traps. We posit at least 5 different individuals from these 17 camera trap detections across the survey grid. This is corroborated by 5 snow leopard scats as confirmed by DNA scatology. Three of the five scats came from different individuals (two males, one female); the other two scats could not be analysed down to individual level. This transition from highly restricted captures to an expansive grid-scale detection window marks a shift from simple presence confirmation to an active evaluation of regional density, habitat connectivity and spatial distribution.

Distributing 17 detections and up to five distinct individuals (with at least three definitively separated by DNA scatology, including one male and one female) across a 520 square km landscape aligns seamlessly with established telemetry and home range literature. Adult snow leopards maintain large home ranges that reflect prey availability, averaging roughly 120 square km for females and well over 200 square km for males (Pålsson, unpublished). Capturing five distinct individuals within a 520 square km block indicates that the survey area captures a contiguous network of overlapping resident territories rather than random, isolated transients. This extensive spatial tracking is further strengthened by the molecular data; while previous expeditions often struggled with sample contamination from sympatric carnivores such as red foxes or Mongolian wolves (Mambetov & Hammer 2023), the 2025 DNA validation of both male and female genotypes suggests a functional, reproducing population structure operating across the valley systems.

When evaluated against broader regional research, the population density implied by five individuals across 520 square km reflects healthy, stable habitats in Central Asia. For instance, robust spatial capture-recapture (SCR) modeling in the Yage Valley of the Sanjiangyuan region on the Tibetan Plateau in western China documented resident densities of approximately two to three individuals per 100 square km (Zhang et al. 2020), which translates to a highly comparable estimate of 10 to 15 individuals per 500 square km. The steady temporal distribution of the expedition's captures (spanning September 2024 until July 2025) confirms year-round residency within the survey grid. Because this timeline largely skips the seasonal January to March oestrus period (Zaman & Chen 2024, Zaman et al. 2024), we posit that these individuals were moving independently across their respective home ranges rather than traveling concurrently as mating pairs. This points to a well-established spatial partitioning where resident leopards utilise shared landscape corridors over multiple seasons.

Ultimately, these conclusions carry substantial weight for the ongoing conservation objectives of the project. The 2024 expedition report highlighted that while the Teskey Ala-Too range features high-quality alpine habitat, its long-term viability is severely threatened by game ungulate poaching and severe habitat degradation from oversized livestock herds (Zholdosbekov & Hammer 2025). Proving that a minimum of five individuals actively rely on this landscape provides a powerful, data-driven mandate for regional anti-poaching enforcement and community-managed grazing plans. Rather than trying to protect isolated pockets, these results demonstrate that conservation frameworks must operate at a landscape scale to successfully protect the extensive travel corridors and critical prey resources required to sustain this vulnerable Tien Shan population.

Prey and other animals

The 2025 expedition builds significantly upon the foundational surveys initiated since the relocation to the Burkhan and Archaly valleys. Across the study site, the spatial distribution of prey and sympatric carnivores highlights a species richness that largely aligns with broader Central Asian trends, yet reveals highly localised population dynamics. Methodologies utilising grid-cell data collection successfully minimised data autocorrelation, providing insights into habitat quality, connectivity and seasonal resource availability for the regional snow leopard population.

Consistent with historical records from previous study sites across the Tien Shan mountains, small mammals and ungulates comprise the primary prey base in the valley systems. The grey marmot was confirmed as the most ubiquitous prey species, documented across 80 of the 98 surveyed cells via direct sightings, burrows, scat, calls and camera trap captures. This extensive presence matches the 2024 findings, where marmots were similarly noted as the most frequently recorded prey species (96 cells). Additionally, high occupancy rates for high-altitude small game were maintained by the Tolai hare, which was recorded across 28 grid cells. Moles were also frequently documented, with active burrows, scats and tracks identified in 29 cells.

Among large game ungulates, the Siberian ibex remains the primary large prey resource for local apex predators, though its distribution shows distinct spatial patterning. The 2025 survey recorded ibex herds and signs in 24 separate cells, primarily through diurnal camera

trap data, scats and physical remains. This reflects a slight spatial contraction compared to the 34 cells recorded in 2024, though herd sizes captured on camera (including groups of 15 to 29 individuals) point to a stable resident population. In stark contrast, the status of the transboundary argali continues to be critically precarious, with the species remaining very rare within the study area. Continuing a downward trend observed across multiple historical expedition sites, argali presence was restricted to just two cells in 2025, verified only by a single camera trap photograph and an old horn. This mirrors the scarce 2024 data, where argali was found in only three cells. This persistent scarcity is highly likely driven by illegal hunting, as direct evidence of poaching targeting both ibex and argali was found across six cells during the survey.

The carnivore guild within the study site is characterised by high detection rates of widespread mesopredators and pervasive threats from larger competitors. The red fox and the stone marten exhibited high landscape occupancy, recorded in 15 and 14 cells respectively, predominantly via nocturnal camera trapping. The Asian badger was another highly prevalent non-prey mammal, verified across 20 cells. Most notably, the highly elusive Pallas's cat or manul was confirmed in two distinct cells. Given the cryptic nature and specific habitat requirements of this felid, its detection represents an unusual and highly significant finding for the regional distribution baseline.

Conversely, the Mongolian wolf remains the most dominant and widespread large competitor, recorded across 14 cells through direct sightings, camera traps, and scats. Genetic analysis of collected scats revealed a persistent overlap in range; out of nine scats originally presumed to belong to snow leopards, one was molecularly identified as Mongolian wolf. This high wolf prevalence directly correlates with local herder interviews, which universally cited the wolf as the premier threat to domestic livestock and the primary target of active human persecution and state-backed bounties.

Ultimately, the 2025 findings underscore that while the Teskey Ala-Too range supports a diverse and functional trophic web capable of sustaining at least five distinct, resident snow leopards, the ecosystem faces severe anthropogenic pressure. Direct evidence of poaching remains a pressing issue, mirroring the exact number of poaching cells flagged during the 2024 expedition. Furthermore, field observations and interviews with 17 local shepherd families indicate that significant overgrazing by oversized, thousands-strong sheep herds poses an imminent threat to the fragile alpine pastures. Combined with the rapid spread of the invasive shrub *Caragana frutex*, which dense growth patterns actively restrict the foraging movements of small mammals such as marmots and badgers, these threats risk fracturing critical habitat corridors. To transition this significant alpine habitat into a permanent stronghold for snow leopards and their wild prey, immediate conservation frameworks should focus on stringent anti-poaching enforcement and community-managed livestock grazing plans.

Interviews and community engagement

The expedition sought to introduce its research to the local community, involve them in conservation decisions, integrate their traditional knowledge and provide economic benefits.

The community: The population consists primarily of family-based shepherds who do not own the land or most of the livestock they tend (owning only 10–15%). They lease pasture

plots from village authorities and manage massive sheep herds from May to October in Burkhan valley, though Archaly valley shepherds remain year-round. While maintaining their traditional lifestyle, herders highly value education and desire different career paths for their children.

Attitudes towards wildlife and conservation: Snow leopards are admired and tolerated because their impact on daily life is negligible and livestock predation concerns decrease at lower altitudes. Conversely, wolves are heavily disliked and actively hunted due to the threat they pose to livestock, supported by state bounties. Compared to 2024, there is a noticeable shift toward conservation acceptance. Local shepherds even joked that the expedition's widespread camera traps were successfully interfering with their hunting.

Economic impact and tourism: There was strong local interest in tourism as an alternative income stream. Shepherd families generated revenue by selling food, dairy products and traditional wool handicrafts to the expedition and citizen scientists, with several families hosting the team for paid traditional meals.

Poaching and pasture suspicions: While interview answers were generally deemed accurate, there was a clear undercurrent of poaching, particularly targeting ungulates like ibex for meat. In addition, herders frequently wanted to know the location of camera traps. The team believes this stems from a fear of being caught poaching, which many herders culturally view as their right. Poaching is most prevalent in the Archaly valley due to the shepherds' year-round presence and the ease of winter hunting. Some shepherds offered contrived excuses when caught tracking citizen scientists to locate cameras.

Animal encounters: During the interview, shepherds claimed that the area was home to bears *Ursus arctos isabellinus*, roe deer *Capreolus pygargus* and lynx *Lynx Lynx isabellinus*. In particular, the shepherd Ishenbek claimed that in winter, bears break into huts and damage property. He claimed to have seen roe deer on the slopes of the Zhetim-Bel range.

Environmental concerns: Locals and researchers noted several ecological anxieties threatening the pasture lands: (1) Unpredictable weather shifts, prolonged downpours and droughts, (2) shrinking glaciers and dropping water levels in the Burkhan river tributaries, (3) the spread of the invasive plant *Caragana frutex*. Shepherds burn these bushes to save pasture space and the expedition's data suggests that the plant's dense growth actively restricts the movement of local wildlife such as marmots and badgers.

Overall conclusions

The cumulative findings from the 2025 expedition underscore that the Teskey Ala-Too range possesses the foundational ecological architecture required to serve as a vital, long-term stronghold for the regional snow leopard population. Building directly upon the biological baselines established during all expedition surveys in the study site, the current data confirms a highly functional, multi-tiered trophic web. The widespread distribution of essential small mammal prey, such as the grey marmot, alongside a resilient resident population of Siberian ibex, provides a reliable biomass base evidently capable of sustaining at least five distinct apex predators. Furthermore, unique and unusual bio-indicators (such as the documented presence of the cryptic Pallas's cat or manul) signify areas of exceptional habitat quality and high species richness that elevate the conservation value of this entire landscape.

However, the long-term viability of this alpine ecosystem remains severely jeopardised by escalating anthropogenic pressures that threaten to fracture critical habitat corridors. The acute scarcity of the transboundary argali, coupled with direct evidence of illegal hunting across multiple tracking cells, reveals that poaching remains an unabated threat to the region's large ungulates. This strain is compounded by the unregulated expansion of domestic livestock grazing and the encroachment of the invasive shrub *Caragana frutex*, both of which actively degrade and restrict vital foraging grounds for primary prey species. Additionally, the high landscape occupancy of the Mongolian wolf and the resulting intense human-wildlife conflict introduce a volatile predator-herder dynamic, as intense human persecution and state-backed bounties add unpredictable disruptions to the apex competitor guild.

To safeguard the future of the Teskey Ala-Too range, conservation frameworks must urgently transition from baseline data collection to active, landscape-scale management. Addressing the dual threats of poaching and habitat degradation requires the implementation of stringent anti-poaching enforcement alongside collaborative, community-managed livestock grazing plans with local shepherd families. Only by mitigating these human-induced stressors and stabilising the predator-competitor balance can this critical corridor be preserved as a permanent, secure sanctuary for the snow leopard and its wild prey base. However, this must be driven by national and regional bodies with a permanent presence in Kyrgyzstan. The role of Biosphere Expeditions, as a small research and data-collection NGO that provides baseline data and conservation recommendations and is only on site in Kyrgyzstan during expedition periods, can neither be lobbying, nor does it have the authority or resources to establish community-managed protected areas.

Closing remarks

Ultimately, the execution of these critical conservation frameworks cannot rely solely on transient interventions; it must be driven by national and regional bodies with a permanent, year-round presence in Kyrgyzstan. The role of Biosphere Expeditions remains distinct and defined: as a small research and data-collection NGO, its mission is to provide the vital baseline data, scientific insights and conservation recommendations necessary to inform long-term strategy. Operating on site in Kyrgyzstan exclusively during active expedition periods, Biosphere Expeditions does not possess the political mandate for lobbying, nor does it have the institutional authority or resources required to establish and maintain community-managed protected areas. The responsibility for transforming these scientific findings into permanent landscape protection rests with the sovereign and regional authorities capable of enacting lasting legislative change.

Priorities for the next expedition

To build upon the insights gained from the 2025 and previous surveys, the 2026 expedition will focus on expanding spatial coverage, refining individual animal identification and deepening community integration.

Spatial expansion and continued monitoring: Field surveys will be systematically extended further into the Archaly valley ranges to map critical habitat connectivity. The expedition will

maintain its core research mandate, generating the robust baseline data required to formulate adaptive conservation recommendations.

Advanced camera trap deployment: Camera trap stations will be strategically upgraded to utilise dual-side photography setups. Capturing animals simultaneously from both sides will significantly increase the accuracy of individual identification, particularly for snow leopards, by allowing researchers to match unique spot coat patterns from both profiles.

Community integration and off-season maintenance: To ensure data continuity, the expedition will focus on strengthening cooperation with local communities. This includes identifying and training local residents to safely maintain and monitor camera traps during the interim periods between active expeditions.

Stakeholder engagement and advocacy: The expedition will continue to communicate actively with regional and national stakeholders, in an effort to put this report and its critical conclusions in front of key decision-makers to catalyse formal conservation actions.

2.4. Literature cited

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Appendix I: Overview of camera trap results. See also Appendix IV for other species of interest photographed.

No.	Cell	Species recorded	Placed on	Removed on	Total pictures taken	Wild animals	Live-stock	Snow leopard
BE02	L-13	Snow leopard, Fox, Ibex, Stone marten, Snowcock	15.08.2024	25.07.2025	929	164	-	3
BE06	J-06	Ibex, Red fox, Plain Mountain finch	10.08.2024	10.07.2025	98	56	-	-
BE07	Q-08	Ibex	11.08.2024	31.07.2025	57	39	-	-
BE08	J-05	Ibex, Mustelid, Snowcock, Bird, Rodent	10.08.2024	10.07.2025	396	198	-	-
BE09	M-02	Red fox, Badger, Bird	14.08.2024	11.07.2025	129	52	5	-
BE13	K-07	Snow leopard, Ibex, Snowcock, Mustelid, Red fox, Human hunters, Gldenstadt's redstart, Red-billed cough	07.08.2024	17.07.2025	971	780	-	23
BE14	P-08	Ibex, Tolai hare, Lammergeyer, Plain Mountain finch	08.08.2024	11.07.2025	10 515	1036	-	-
BE15	O-09	Snow leopard, Mustelid, Ibex, Red fox, Marmot, Tolai hare, Manul, Plain Mountain finch, Lammergeyer	15.07.2024	12.07.2025	677	282	-	65
BE16	L-12	Snow leopard, Manul, Red fox, Mustelid, Argali, Snowcock	14.08.2024	16.07.2025	195	114	-	6
BE18	L-12	Snow leopard, Ibex, Snowcock	14.08.2024	16.07.2025	132	44	-	6
BE19	O-10	Yak, Plain Mountain finch	19.07.2024	12.07.2025	809	48	46	-
BE23	I-13	-	03.07.2024	16.07.2025	153	-	-	-
BE24	O-11	Snow leopard, Ibex, Red fox	02.08.2024	24.07.2025	153	25	-	3
BE25	O-13	Snow leopard, Ibex, Snowcock	12.08.2023	12.07.2025	129	156	-	3
BE30	O-13	Red-Billed Chough	14.08.2024	12.07.2025	138	24	-	-
BE35	P-09	Snow leopard, Ibex, Snowcock	08.08.2024	11.08.2025	211	108	-	3

Appendix II: Summary of DNA samples collected

Date collected	Cell	Species	Individual	Sample type
16.07.2025	L-12*	Snow leopard	PMSat003m (male)	Scat
16.07.2025	L-12*	Snow leopard	Could not be determined due to low quality sample	Scat
17.07.2025	K-07**	Snow leopard	PMSat001m (male)	Scat
17.07.2025	K-07**	Snow leopard	PMSat002f (female)	Scat
17.07.2025	K-07**	Snow leopard	Could not be determined due to low quality sample	Scat
12.08.2025	W-05	Wolf	Non-snow leopard samples were excluded from genetic analysis down to individual level	Scat
12.08.2025	T-06	Red fox	Non-snow leopard samples were excluded from genetic analysis down to individual level	Scat
31.07.2025	Q-09	Can not determined		Scat
10.07.2025	I-02	Can not determined		Scat

*The two scats in L-12 were found on 16 July 2025 on a ridgeline on the way to camera traps BE16 and BE18, about 2.5 km further up the ridge (or 1.3 km as the crow flies). Both camera traps were placed by the previous expedition on 14 August 2024, 9 m apart with BE16 facing north and BE 18 north-east. They recorded snow leopard two days later on 16 August 2024 and again on 9 September 2024 and 6 June 2025. Camera trap picture analysis identified two probable individuals, DNA scat analysis of the scats found on 16 July 2025 1.3 km down the ridge from the camera traps recorded male PMSat003m at the individual level and another snow leopard scat, which could not be analysed down to the individual level due to low sample quality. On 16 July 2025 BE18 was moved by the current expedition to the location where the scats were found and remains in place there. BE16 remains in its original place with fresh batteries and SD card. SD cards of both will be checked during the 2026 expedition. It is unknown, but likely that scats and photos are associated with the same individual or individuals.

**Scats in K-07 were all collected at the same spot on the same day (17 July 2025), all within a few metres of camera trap BE10, which was found face down and therefore did not record pictures. It is unknown whether the camera trap was manipulated by hunters captured by camera trap BE13 or whether it fell out of its stone cairn through weather, animal action or bad placement.

Appendix III: List of birds recorded by the expedition

This list is mainly a result of citizen scientists with an affinity for birding over the years 2023-2025 recording the species they encountered. Ibisbill (seen in the Burkhan river valley) was added to this list by Johan Mees in 2025.

Common name	Scientific name	Sighting	Camera trap
Black Kite	<i>Milvus migrans</i>	✓	
Brandt's Mountain Finch	<i>Leucosticte brandti</i>	✓	
Chukar	<i>Alectoris chukar</i>	✓	
Cinereous Vulture	<i>Aegypius monachus</i>	✓	
Common Raven	<i>Corvus corax</i>	✓	
Common Redshank	<i>Tringa totanus</i>	✓	
Common Rose Finch	<i>Carpodacus erythrinus</i>	✓	
Common Swift	<i>Apus apus</i>	✓	
Citrine Wagtail	<i>Motacilla citreola</i>	✓	
Crested Lark	<i>Galerida Cristata</i>	✓	
Egyptian Vulture	<i>Neophron percnopterus</i>	✓	
Eurasian Hobby	<i>Falco subbuteo</i>	✓	
Golden Eagle	<i>Aquila chrysaetos</i>	✓	
Goosander	<i>Mergus merganser</i>	✓	
Güldenstadt's Redstart	<i>Phoenicurus erythrogaster</i>	✓	✓
Eurasian Hoopoe	<i>Upupa epops</i>	✓	
Himalayan Griffon Vulture	<i>Gyps himalayensis</i>	✓	
Himalayan Snowcock	<i>Tetraogallus himalayensis</i>	✓	✓
Horned Lark	<i>Eremophila alpestris</i>	✓	
House Martin	<i>Delichon dasypus</i>	✓	
Ibisbill	<i>Ibidorhyncha struthersii</i>	✓	
Isabelline Wheatear	<i>Oenanthe isabellina</i>	✓	
Lammergeier	<i>Gypaetus barbatus</i>	✓	✓
Little Owl	<i>Athene noctua</i>	✓	
Long-Legged Buzzard	<i>Buteo rufinus</i>	✓	
Marsch Harrier	<i>Circus aeruginosus</i>	✓	
Meadow Pipit	<i>Anthus pratensis</i>	✓	
Plain Mountain Finch	<i>Leucosticte nemoricola</i>	✓	✓
Red-Billed Chough	<i>Pyrrhcorax pyrrhcorax</i>	✓	✓
Red-Breasted Goose	<i>Branta ruficollis</i>	✓	
Rock Bunting	<i>Emberiza cia par</i>	✓	
Ruddy Shelduck	<i>Tadorna ferruginea</i>	✓	
Saker Falcon	<i>Falco cherrug</i>	✓	
Swallow	<i>Hirundo rustica</i>	✓	
Upland Buzzard	<i>Buteo hemilasius</i>	✓	
Water Pipit	<i>Anthus spinoletta</i>	✓	
White-Capped Redstart	<i>Chaimarrornis leucocephalus</i>	✓	
White-Rumped Vulture	<i>Gyps bengalensis</i>	✓	
White-Tailed Eagle	<i>Haliaeetus albicilla</i>	✓	
White-Tailed Rubythroat	<i>Luscinia pectoralis ssp. ballioni</i>	✓	
White Throated Dipper	<i>Cinclus cinclus</i>	✓	
White-Winged Snowfinch	<i>Montifringilla nivalis</i>		✓

Appendix IV: Other species of interest recorded by camera trap.

Himalayan snowcock recorded by camera traps BE02 / BE08 / BE13 / BE16 / BE18 / BE25.

Yellow-billed chough recorded by camera trap BE13 / Lammergeier recorded by camera trap BE14 / Red-billed chough by camera trap BE30.

Snowcock by camera trap BE30

Appendix V: Environmental impact at base camp

Situation when leaving base camp on 17 August 2024. The circles indicate where yurts had stood, the smaller squares dome tent positions and the brown space, areas that had been walked on often.

Situation when arriving at base camp on 2 July 2025.